

RESEARCH OF EFFECTIVE METHODS IN TEACHING ARTISTIC LITERATURE

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Abstract. *Providing information about the issue of integration and competence in the teaching of fiction. Explain the advantages of the "Research method", "Re-scripting", "Contrast method", "Feeling the character" methods tested in the experiment.*

Keywords: *linguistic rhythm, integration, competence, method, "Research method", "Re-scripting", contrast.*

Fiction is a necessary source of knowledge that helps to understand and analyze various situations in a person's daily life. For this reason, the issue of teaching works of art is always relevant. In order for there to be a dialogue between the teacher and the student, the teacher must have enough skills, experience and skills, and he must always ask himself "What should be taught?", "How should it be taught?", "Why should it be taught in such and such a way?" should ask questions. It is important for literature teachers to pay attention to the following when preparing for the lesson:

1. Setting the goal (What will I teach?).
2. Respecting the personality of the student.
3. Demanding.
4. Do not use punishment methods inappropriately.
5. Connecting the topic with life.
6. Analysis, generalization, conclusion.
7. Thorough preparation for the lesson.
8. Always use new pedagogical technology in class.

The use of new forms of teaching in literature classes is also a demand of the times. The use of new methods such as "Discussion", "Brainstorming", "6x6x6", "Role-playing games", "Choose a place for yourself", "Working with groups" in the training will certainly have a good effect. The newly adopted Law "On Education" in the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Education Programs specifically emphasize the following knowledge, skills and abilities that should be developed in students of literature:

- Understanding the social function of fiction in glorifying national and universal values;
- Knowing the contribution of Uzbek literary and artistic heritage to the development of world literature;
- To be able to evaluate a work of art from an ideological-artistic point of view, to be able to distinguish the writer's attitude to life, the skill of using the artistic and figurative means of language in expressing it;
- Expressive reading, interpretation of samples of Uzbek classic literature, knowledge of genre features;
- To know the principles of formation and development of Uzbek literature of the 20th century;

- To be able to understand and analyze the artistic and aesthetic significance of the studied work;
- To be able to think independently and creatively about the heroes of the work, to be able to describe them, to be able to write a summary, an essay explaining the essence and artistry of the work of art;
- Being able to independently assess the heroes of the work from the point of view of universal and national values;
- Knowing the interaction of Uzbek literature with world literature.

From the above criteria: To be able to independently evaluate the heroes of the work from the point of view of universal and national values, and to focus on the methods of knowing the directions of interaction of Uzbek literature with world literature, lecturers and teachers of literature if he uses linguistic rhythms in explanation and analysis, his theoretical information on the subject will be effective and understandable for students. Linguistic rhythm - the rhythm in poetry is the expression of the tone of words that appears on the basis of sound at different frequencies. To use the linguistic rhythm, first of all: when giving theoretical information on the topic, pronounce the words that give the main meaning slowly, expressively (with emphasis); secondly, if one is analyzing the speech of the heroes in a work of art, it is necessary to bring out the emotional tone, mentality, and appearance of these heroes. Then mastering the lesson will be higher. If the pedagogue cannot create a speech situation in linguistic rhythm through his person, he can use media tools. For example, showing audio and video materials recorded from stage productions has a good effect.

Also, the issue of integration is important in any literary education, it forms the concept of compatibility of the reality of life and artistic reality in the thinking of students. The term integration is derived from the Latin word "integration" which means "joining", "uniting". There are basically two directions of integration in teaching literature:

- integration of individual training of students in certain directions;
- integration of the creative team of experts and students.

Through integration, students can combine the knowledge and skills they have acquired in other subjects with the issues they have understood from fiction. For example, in understanding the essence of literary materials such as Albert Camus's story "The Stranger", it is appropriate to rely on the connection with jurisprudence, sociology, philosophy, that is, to integrate the knowledge acquired during the study of these academic subjects. It is necessary for students to be able to apply the knowledge gained from artistic works in their professional activities. This requires attention to competence. Competence (from the Latin "competens" - means worthy, suitable, necessary, capable, capable) - a concept that means the presence of knowledge, skills, qualifications and experience necessary for effective activity in certain areas of life by a person. Competence is the possession of competence. It means the harmony between a person's personal qualities and the knowledge, skills and experience necessary for effective activity in certain areas. Every professional has an exciting and productive potential. Professional competence means acquisition of knowledge necessary for professional activity by a specialist and their practical application at a high level.

In the course of the lesson, it is necessary to use methods that are appropriate for the students' worldview, age, and have relevant content. Method - (Greek "methodos" - a way of knowing or research, theory, teaching) - practical and theoretical acquisition of reality, mastering,

learning, guidelines for knowing, a set of methods, a method of creating and justifying philosophical knowledge. Scientific theories tested in practice form the main content of scientific methods. It is desirable for the teacher to be able to put a unique problem in the work in front of each student and direct him to solve it. In such situations, the "Research method" method can be used. The research method assumes that some difficult theoretical issues will be raised during the educational process. This method requires independent application of effective research methods of education at a relatively high stage of learning. In this, students perform practical tasks such as gathering evidence and their theoretical analysis, systematization, generalization, and drawing scientific conclusions. In this case, before the student gives information about the solutions to the problem in the work of art:

- carefully studies the text of the work;
- studies stylistics;
- finds facts in context;
- remembers words of academic level in the language;
- develops the student's cognitive process, ability to observe.

Another effective method of teaching fiction is the method of "rewriting the script". In this method, students should rewrite the script created by the writer, that is, based on their worldview, the development of events. It can express the character of the characters in the work in a different way. The teacher can give tasks such as "Write your opinion", "State your attitude", "Justify your opinion". Italian expert J. Rodari said: "If we want to teach children to think independently, first of all, we should encourage them to weave fairy tales and create adventures. Thought should be spent only on new, never-before-seen, controversial issues. "Boredom is the enemy of thought" shows the importance of this method. As a result of using the method, young people develop the following skills:

- thorough study of sentence structure in this language;
- creative ability;
- observational thinking ability;
- self-confidence;

One of the modern methods is the contrast method. Contrast (French *contraste* - sharp contrast) - subjectively exaggerated perception of differences in objects or their parts; a change in sensitivity due to previous or simultaneous stimulation of the opposite quality. Students are asked to write down positive qualities of negative characters in the play or to verbalize the positive aspects of bad events. Through this method, readers can:

- the ability to think logically;
- the ability to think optimistically;
- thoroughness;
- comparative analysis skills will be improved.

The well-known Polish pedagogue W. Okory focused on the principles of discovery and perception of education in order to ensure the student's independent and free thinking during the teaching process. V. Okori wrote about the task of describing the psyche and appearance of a complex character by students in the method of "Feeling the Hero". As the main principle, he emphasized that "the characters of the work should be viewed as living people, not images." In this case, the teacher shows each student a video or photo of a particular character. Through the

method, the student can feel and describe the hero himself, analyze his activities during the work, and explain his achievements and shortcomings in detail. Effective results of the method include:

- allows to activate imagination and emotion;
- develops the ability to understand people;
- helps to understand the relationship between the texts of fiction and its highly imaginative constructions.

These methods, used in 2-year experimental classes, help students to fully understand the work of art and apply knowledge in real life situations. It is also useful for organizing literature lessons in an interactive way. Today, various methods are used in literature education for the development of human capital and society. Therefore, the appropriate use of innovative and effective methods of education is the guarantee of the effectiveness of literary education.

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